

A QUANTITATIVE STUDY OF TEACHING ESL THROUGH VERBAL BEHAVIOR PRACTICES IN PRIVATE SECTOR HIGH SCHOOLS OF LAHORE, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The purpose of this quantitative study is to examine the verbal behavior practices used by English Language Teachers (ELTs) for teaching English as a second language in the private-sector high schools in Lahore, Pakistan. The study is grounded in B. F. Skinner's (1957) behaviorist theory. A convenience sampling technique was employed to select one hundred English-language teachers from five private-sector English-medium high schools in Lahore, Pakistan. To increase heterogeneity, schools were sampled from different strata of class, environment, and educational quality. An adapted survey questionnaire was used to collect data from English language teachers. The data were analyzed statistically to present the results through tables and charts. The results reveal that teachers frequently use mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbal techniques to teach English as a second language to students. The participants have responded that they mostly use the complex technique of intraverbal before simple techniques of mands, tacts, and echoics. The study finds that only 17% (n=17) of ESL teachers are English Language Teaching (ELT) certified, and 83% (n=83) are non-certified. The study recommends that verbal behavior practices should be used in the classrooms by the

Keywords: *Echoics, English as a Second Language (ESL), English Language Teachers (ELTs), Intraverbal, Mands, Tacts, Verbal Behavior Practices*

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Language is the reflection of mental images through speech and writing (Mahmood, 2020: 56). Abukhattala (2013) describes language acquisition and learning phenomenon in the L2 classroom environment, where learning is preferred over acquisition of language. English language teachers impart lexical, structural, and phonological knowledge of the target language and expect accurate feedback from learners. In sequence to the input of the second language, learners are encouraged to practice and showcase their functional competence of the second language.

English language teachers across the globe apply different language teaching techniques and activities in classrooms to impart a second language to the learners. Raja (2014) enumerates different second language teaching and learning methods ranging from demonstration, grammar-translation method, direct method, communicative language teaching, techniques, strategies, multimedia, technology, visual aids, audio-lingual method, explanation, vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, communication skills, and practice. However, verbal behavior language teaching practices such as mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbal are also used by the teachers to teach English as a second language. Pino, O. et al (2010) support this notion that during the recent decades researchers have brought about contribution to the study of language development acquisition based on Skinner's verbal behavior analysis.

Mands are verbal responses reinforced by a specific consequence and under the functional control of motivational variables and sustained by specific consequences (Skinner, 1957). He defines tact as a verbal operant in which a response is evoked by an object or an event, or by one or more of its features. In the tact, the response specifies a feature of a stimulus and is maintained by generalized reinforcement. Echoic is defined as verbal behavior that shares point-to-point correspondence with the vocal-verbal stimulus that evokes it. Acquisition of other verbal operants may be facilitated by a strong echoic repertoire, including the self-echoic (Skinner, p. 64), in which a speaker who hears his or her own "response" (as auditory stimuli) echoes those self-produced stimuli. Such self-echoic responding can be reinforced automatically if its emission controls further aspects of the speaker's verbal behavior (Vaughan & Michael, 1982).

As far as intraverbal behavior is concerned, Skinner (1957) defines it as verbal responses that lack point-to-point correspondence with an antecedent verbal stimulus. These four aspects of verbal behavior are categorized into simple and complex. Mands, tacts, and echoics are the simple and intraverbal behaviors, which are considered complex verbal behavior techniques.

Pakistan is a country situated in the South Asian region. It came into being on August 14, 1947, after the ninety-year British colonial era. The English language is a de facto official language of the country despite the September 2015 verdict of the Supreme Court of Pakistan, declaring Urdu as the official and national language. English is learned by students in classroom settings from pre-school to higher education. There are certain strata of schools in Pakistan imparting the English language to learners as a second language. These are elite schools of the Cambridge and Oxford education system, upper, middle, lower middle, and lower strata English medium institutions. English language teachers apply different modern and obsolete L2 teaching methods in the classroom. It is assumed that verbal behavior technique or practice is one of the strategies to teach English as a second language in the schools of Pakistan.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the verbal behavior practices used by English language teachers in English medium high schools in Lahore and their eligibility, in terms of certification to teach English as a second language to students.

1.3. Research Questions

This study has addressed three research questions as follows:

- What is the frequency of using verbal behavior practices (mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbals) for teaching English in Pakistan by English Language Teachers (ELTs)?
- What is the frequency of using simple verbal behavior practices: mand, tact, and echoic, before complex practice of intraverbal or vice versa by English Language Teachers (ELTs) in Pakistan?
- Are English Language Teachers (ELTs) hired by the Pakistani high schools certified to teach English as a second language?

1.4. Implications of the Study

Pakistan is a multilingual and multicultural country with a hierarchy of a class system. English as a second language learning is the norm and requirement for examinations and better job opportunities. This study will be an addition to the existing repertoire of the English language teaching as the study has established connections between teaching ESL through verbal behavior practices focusing on teachers' certification for teaching English as a second language. This will guide educational policymakers, language planners, and heads of schools to follow the transparent and merit-based criteria for hiring English language teachers. The ultimate beneficiaries of this research will be the aspiring English language teachers and ESL learners in Pakistan.

1.5. Review of the Literature

English as a global language has engulfed the whole world in terms of learning. This phenomenon is more trending in the outer and expanding circles of The World English(es) countries. The post-colonial countries carry forward the legacy of the English language as the aftermath of their masters. The countries have chalked out policies for the students to learn English as a second language. This also fortifies that higher education, job placement, and futuristic planning are based on the competency of the English language. To impart the learning of the English language, different schools in Pakistan apply different teaching methodologies. Teaching English as a Second Language through verbal behavior practices is one of the techniques used by teachers in schools.

Brown (1994, as cited in Nylund & Wernersson, 2005) shares that B. F. Skinner is the propellant for the *Verbal Behavior* for language learning. He developed this linguistic model of behaviorism as an extension of the theory of learning through reinforcement. This model is structured on the notion that learners learn through the behavior of their surrounding environment. Skinner asserted that language is also learnt in the same way as knowledge is learned through repetition of behaviors and reinforcement.

Parveen et al. (2023), in a study conducted at the college level in the district of Okara of Pakistan, explored the positive, negative, gestural, contact, and proximity reinforcement strategies of teachers to teach English as a second language. This qualitative study collected data through open-ended interviews and observations by the authors. The data analysis showed that the private sector colleges of District Okara used both positive and negative reinforcement while teaching English as a second language in the classrooms. However, it was found that positive reinforcement strategies were beneficial for the students to learn the English language in a better way. Although this study was conducted to observe the verbal and non-verbal reinforcement behavioral practices of English language teachers at the college level, the study does not mention the verbal behavior strategies used by the teachers. Moreover, this study fortifies that verbal behavior strategies are not restricted to primary level students but are even useful at the college level.

Awan & Shafi (2016) conducted a quantitative study with a sample set of three hundred students and thirty teachers from Government high schools for Boys and Girls in the district Dera Ghazi Khan of Pakistan. The data collected through two different survey questionnaires were analyzed using SPSS. The study found that eighty percent of students in the schools of Dera Ghazi Khan showed their liking for the traditional Grammar Translation Method (GTM) for learning English as a second language. However, the study did not mention the response of the teachers. This shows that in the rural areas of Pakistan, the traditional method of Grammar Translation Method is being used by the English language teachers to teach English as a second language. This practice is good for

imparting the structural knowledge of the target language, but is found to be lacking in the verbal communication competency and fluency.

Khan (2011), in a study, highlights the challenges faced by learners of English as a second language. He asserts that teaching and learning English as a second language in non-native settings is a challenging task. The author furthers the point to improve the situation of learning English as a second language. The study recommends that the government and private sector should join hands to chalk out such policies for English language teaching and learning that simplify the process. The teacher's competency and proficiency should be enhanced by implementing the strict hiring criteria with English Language Teaching certification, such as Teaching of English as a Foreign Language (TEFL), English Language Teaching (ELT) degrees, diplomas, and certificates. This will bring qualified English language teachers into the classroom with state-of-the-art technology savvy and other activities to teach English as a second language.

To augment the notion, Mahmood (2020) conducted a study entitled *Academic writing challenges of EFL learners and teachers' proficiency in Pakistani Higher Education*. This research analyzed the proficiency of teachers for teaching academic writing to the English as a Foreign Language learners in the Pakistani context. The quantitative and qualitative data were collected from nineteen MA TEFL students of a public sector university of Pakistan, the Higher Education Commission, and Public Service Commission websites, and newspaper advertisements for the recruitment of English language teachers. The study found that most of the teachers in Pakistan were hired without any prerequisite for a specific English Language Teaching certification. This results in a bad impact on the English learning of the students, and they face academic writing challenges even at the graduate and post-graduate level studies. It is evident that certification and training of teachers play a vital role in teaching a second or foreign language.

Shahreena, Ahmad & Shahabullah (2021), in a study conducted in the underdeveloped district of the province of Punjab in Pakistan, analyzed the English language teaching and learning phenomenon. The study found that the situation of English language teaching in Pakistan is in a deplorable condition. The major challenge behind this situation was termed as the lack of knowledge and communication skills of English language teachers. The situation is equally parallel in both government and private sector elementary schools. English language teachers do not possess adequate teaching skills and methodologies for teaching English as a second language. This study was conducted in the context of English language teachers' communication skills. However, English language teaching techniques and practices like verbal behavior methods have not been discussed or analyzed in this study.

The review of the above literature, narrowed down to the Pakistani context where English is learned as a second language, showcased that these studies have been conducted at the college and university level. However, a limited number of studies have been conducted at the school level and are limited to public sector schools. These studies have analyzed the English as a Second Language teaching and learning phenomenon from different angles, like academic writing challenges, the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), and the qualifications of English Language Teachers (ELTs). One of the studies has been conducted in the backdrop of learning language through reinforcement. But none of the above studies have analyzed the teaching of English as a Second Language through verbal behavior practices. Hence, there is a dearth of literature and a research gap in exploring teaching English as a Second Language through verbal behavior practices in Pakistan. This study has not only filled this gap of research on verbal behavior practices but also explored the phenomenon from the standpoints of the order of the use of simpler to complex or vice versa techniques by the teachers. The aspect of English Language Teachers' (ELTs) language teaching certification has also been analyzed. The study will be a humble contribution to English language teaching through verbal behavior techniques, not only beneficial to Pakistan but also to all the outer and expanding circle countries of the World Englishes. All the English language teachers, school administration, hiring agencies, and language learners will take the lead from this study.

2. Methodology

2.1. Theoretical Framework

B. F. Skinner's (1957) theory of verbal behavior has been employed as the theoretical framework for this study. This theory elaborates verbal behavior as a medium of language learning, in which the listener mediates. It denotes a relation between the speakers' and listeners' social relationships on equal footing. This social relationship could be from any field of life, such as domestic, business, pedagogical, and language learning spheres. In verbal behavior, the speaker accesses the reinforcement in the shape of the listeners' behavior.

2.2. Research Design

This study has been conducted under the quantitative research paradigm to audit the verbal behavior practices used by English Language Teachers (ELTs) to teach English as a second language in private-sector English-medium high schools of Lahore, Pakistan. Goertzen (2017) defines the quantitative research method as the collection and analysis of structured data shown in numbers. This method of research provides reliable and accurate frequencies and measurements.

Survey technique has been used to collect data and answer three research questions focusing on the use of verbal behavior practices by the teachers to teach English as a

second language in Pakistani schools, the utility of these practices from pre-school to grade ten (matriculation), and the qualification of English Language Teachers.

2.3. Sample and Demographics

All the English Language Teachers (ELTs) of private sector middle and lower middle strata English medium high schools of Pakistan were identified as the population for this study. In the first phase, convenience sampling was used to select five English medium high schools based in Lahore, the capital city of the province of the Punjab, Pakistan, also known as a seat of learning in the country. To make data more heterogeneous and representative, the schools were selected keeping in view the status, quality of teaching, environment, and reputation in the locality. These schools were coded as School 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5, respectively, to ensure anonymity and ethical considerations.

In the second phase, all the English Language Teachers (ELTs) teaching English as a second language in the five sampled schools were selected as respondents of the study. A total of one-hundred pre-school to grade ten English Language Teachers responded to the survey questionnaire. According to Cohen, Manion & Morrison (2007), convenience or purposive sampling technique carries along the characteristics of quantitative and qualitative research. The researchers remain at liberty to pick and choose the participants for the sample on the basis of their own knowledge to fulfill the requirements set for the studies. The demographics of the sampled English Language Teachers are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: *Demographics of the Sample*

Number of participants	100
Gender	76 Females & 24 males
Age Group	20 – 50 Years
Mother Tongue	82 Urdu, 15 Punjabi, 2 Saraiki, & 1 Pashto
Certified English Language Teachers	17
Non-Certified English Language Teachers	83

2.4. Instrumentation

An adapted survey questionnaire (Mahmood, 2020) was assimilated to collect data from one hundred English Language Teachers of five sampled English medium high schools based in Lahore, Pakistan (see Appendix A). To establish validity, the questionnaire was approved by two expert academicians and researchers in the field of quantitative research. Certain additions and deletions were made for the compatibility of

the instrument with verbal behavior practices for teaching English as a second language in Pakistan. The survey questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section 1 of the survey questionnaire, with seven closed-ended questions, targets the basic demographics of the respondents, focusing on gender, age, mother tongue, class, years of teaching, academic qualifications, and English language teaching certification. Section 2 of the instrument consists of nine questions on a Likert scale to record the responses of the respondents for teaching the English language through verbal behavior practices. These nine questions were to be answered by ticking one of the six options outlined in front of each question. These likeret scale options were *Always, Mostly, Frequently, Occasionally, Rarely, and Never*.

2.5. Data Collection

The data for this study were collected in different phases from English language teachers of all five sampled schools. In the first phase, school administration, principals, and section heads were contacted and requested to provide the data collection. With the consent of the school administration, the survey questionnaire was distributed among the English language teachers of the sampled schools. For the field work, a research assistant with a degree from a renowned university in Pakistan was hired. After the distribution of one hundred survey sheets to teachers, the field researcher explained to them the procedure for filling out the questionnaire.

All the teachers received the questionnaire, recorded their responses, and returned it to the field research assistant the next day. This recording of responses in the absence of the field research assistant makes the data richer, unbiased, and more reliable. This whole process of seeking permission from the gatekeepers, contacting the respondents, briefing them about data collection, its purpose, and receiving back one hundred filled questionnaire forms from the teachers of five sampled schools spanned over a period of two weeks. In the next phase, the field research assistant checked the questionnaire sheets to ensure that the respondents had filled out all the sections and items. Subsequently, these questionnaire sheets and responses were double-checked by the author to stamp the correctness of the data. Finally, data presentation and compilation were done in Microsoft Excel through tables and charts for the analysis.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

This survey-based study raised certain ethical issues for the researcher. To comply with the ethical considerations, the data were collected from the English Language Teachers of the five sampled schools of Lahore, Pakistan. The anonymity of the respondents was ensured, and the name column was not added in section 1 of the questionnaire. The security of the data was taken care of by handling and keeping the data in the safe custody of the author. In this way, the risk of breach, alteration, loss, or

unauthorized access to the data was shielded. Moreover, principles of ethical considerations recommended by Shamoo & Resnik (2009) were followed in true letter and spirit during handling, presentation, and analysis. They proposed the principles of honesty, objectivity, integrity, carefulness, openness, and respect for intellectual property, confidentiality, responsible publication, social responsibility, non-discrimination, competence, and legality.

3. Results

The study examined the verbal behavior practices used by English language teachers in English medium high schools of Lahore, Pakistan. The study set two research questions: (1) *What is the frequency of using verbal behavior practices (mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbal) for teaching ESL in Pakistan by English Language Teachers (ELTs)?* (2) *What is the frequency of using simple verbal behavior practices: mands, tacts, and echoics, before complex practice of intraverbal or vice versa by English Language Teachers (ELTs) in Pakistan?* (3) *Are English Language Teachers (ELTs) hired by the Pakistani high schools certified to teach English as a Second Language?* The data collected from one hundred English language teachers of five sampled private sector English medium schools through a survey questionnaire were analyzed to address the above research questions. The analysis of the data is presented below in tables, charts, and described in the discussion section:

3.1. Use of verbal behavior practices in the classroom by English Language Teachers

To address the first research question, “*What is the frequency of using verbal behavior practices (mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbals) by the English Language Teachers to teach English as a Second Language in Pakistan?*” data collected through section 2 of the questionnaire were analyzed. The data showed varying frequencies of the use of verbal behavior practices as displayed in Table 2 below:

Table 2 *Frequency of Verbal Behavior Practices by English Language Teachers (ELTs)*

Practices	Response					
	Always	Mostly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
Mands Technique	18	45	16	14	7	0
Tacts Technique	36	35	18	9	2	0
Echoics Technique	23	43	23	7	4	0

Practices	Response					
	Always	Mostly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
Echoics Impact on Mands & Tacts	31	24	22	17	6	0
Intraverbal Technique	30	42	14	7	6	1
Intraverbal Technique Difficulty	16	35	25	11	11	2
Mands, Tacts, Echoics, Intraverbal Order	16	35	24	18	4	3
Intraverbal, Mands, Tacts, Echoics Order	26	38	21	10	1	4
Useful for Primary Students Only	17	15	10	16	9	33
Intraverbal Technique	30	42	14	7	6	1

According to the data analyzed in Table 2 above, 18% (n=18) participants responded 'Always', 45% (n=45) 'Mostly', 16% (n=16) 'Frequently', 14% (n=14) 'Occasionally', 7% (n=7) 'Rarely', and 0% (n=0) 'Never' for using mands technique in the classroom for teaching English as second language.

For tacts technique, 36% (n=36) responded 'Always', 35% (n=35) 'Mostly', 18% (n=18) 'Frequently', 9% (n=9) 'Occasionally', 2% (n=2) 'Rarely', and 0% (n=0) 'Never'.

As far as the echoics technique is concerned, 23% (n=23) responded 'Always', 43% (n=43) 'Mostly', 23% (n=23) 'Frequently', 7% (n=7) 'Occasionally', 4% (n=4) 'Rarely', and 0% (n=0) 'Never'.

For the intraverbal technique, 30% (n=30) responded 'Always', 42% (n=42) 'Mostly', 14% (n=14) 'Frequently', 7% (n=7) 'Occasionally', 6% (n=6) 'Rarely', and 1% (n=1) 'Never'.

To ascertain the perception of teachers about intraverbal technique as difficult as compared to mands, tacts, and echoics, 16% (n=16) responded ‘Always’, 35% (n=35) ‘Mostly’, 25% (n=25) ‘Frequently’, 11% (n=11) ‘Occasionally’, 11% (n=11) ‘Rarely’, and 2% (n=2) ‘Never’.

16% (n=16) teachers responded ‘Always’, 35% (n=35) ‘Mostly’, 24% (n=24) ‘Frequently’, 18% (n=18) ‘Occasionally’, 4% (n=4) ‘Rarely’, and 3% (n=3) ‘Never’ for teaching English language through verbal behavior practices order of mands, tacts, and echoics.

However, 26% (n=26) teachers responded ‘Always’, 38% (n=38) ‘Mostly’, 21% (n=21) ‘Frequently’, 10% (n=10) ‘Occasionally’, 1% (n=1) ‘Rarely’, and 4% (n=4) ‘Never’.

In response to the question that verbal behavior practices for teaching English as second language is useful for primary level students only, 17% (n=17) participants responded ‘Always’, 15% (n=15) ‘Mostly’, 10% (n=10) ‘Frequently’, 16% (n=16) ‘Occasionally’, 9% (n=9) ‘Rarely’, and 33% (n=33) ‘Never’. The above results have been shown graphically in the chart in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Frequency of Use of Verbal Behavior Practices by English Language Teachers (ELTs)

3.2. Use of simple verbal behavior techniques before the complex technique of intraverbal or vice versa

To address the second research question, “*Do English Language Teachers (ELTs) use simple verbal behavior practices, i.e., mands, tacts, and echoics before complex practice of intraverbal or vice versa?*” 16% (n=16) teachers responded ‘Always’, 35% (n=35) ‘Mostly’, 24% (n=24) ‘Frequently’, 18% (n=18) ‘Occasionally’, 4% (n=4) ‘Rarely’, and 3% (n=3) ‘Never’ for teaching English language through verbal behavior practices order of mands, tacts, and echoics.

However, for use of intraverbal before simple techniques of mands, tacts, and echoics, 26% (n=26) teachers responded ‘Always’, 38% (n=38) ‘Mostly’, 21% (n=21) ‘Frequently’, 10% (n=10) ‘Occasionally’, 1% (n=1) ‘Rarely’, and 4% (n=4) ‘Never’. Responses of the participants for the order of using simple to complex verbal behavior techniques or vice versa are shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3: *The Order of Simple to Complex Verbal Behavior Techniques and vice versa*

Frequency	Order of use of simple to complex and complex to simple verbal behavior techniques	
	Simple techniques (mands, tacts, echoics)	Complex technique (intraverbal)
Always	16	26
Mostly	35	38
Frequently	24	21
Occasionally	18	10
Rarely	4	1
Never	3	4

The above frequency of the order of use of simpler to complex or complex to simpler verbal behavior techniques is shown in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2: *Order of the Use of Simpler to Complex Techniques or vice versa*

3.3. Certified vs. Non-certified English Language Teachers

To address the third research question, “*Are ELTs hired by the Pakistani schools certified to teach English as a second language?*” the responses of the participants show that 17% (n=17) of teachers hold the certification for teaching English as a second language. However, 83% (n=83) of respondents are teaching ESL in the classroom without having any local or international certification of ELT. School-wise breakdown of certified and non-certified ELTs is shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4: *Certified vs Non-certified English Language Teachers*

Schools	Certified ELTs	Non Certified ELTs	Total
School 1	4	19	23
School 2	4	14	18
School 3	3	14	17
School 4	5	12	17
School 5	1	24	25
Total:	17	83	100

Figure 3 below further elaborates the data shown in Table 4 above in the shape of a chart:

Figure 3: *Certified vs Non-Certified English Language Teachers (ELTs)*

4. Discussion

The analysis of the data collected from one hundred English language teachers of five sampled private sector English medium high schools based in Lahore, the capital city of the province of Punjab, Pakistan, has showcased multidimensional results and trends of teaching English as a second language through verbal behavior techniques. The emerging trend of the data showed that on the Likert scale, the frequency of using verbal behavior techniques in the classroom by the teachers varies from one technique to another.

All the simple verbal behavior practices like mands, tacts, and echoics are used mostly by the teachers in the classroom to teach the English language. The frequency of not using these techniques in the classroom is almost insignificant. Moreover, this frequency is homogenous for the complex verbal behavior practice, i.e., intraverbal, and teachers also use this technique mostly in the classroom. This trend in the frequency shows that there is no significant difference in the use of simple and complex verbal behavior techniques for teaching English as a second language.

The other major trend found in the data was that teachers mostly find these verbal techniques difficult to use in the classroom, and they observe students facing difficulty in comprehending language through these verbal behavior practices. As far as the order of using simple and complex verbal behavior practices is concerned, the analysis portrayed that English language teachers mostly used intraverbal behavior techniques more than the simple verbal behavior techniques of mands, tacts, and echoics.

Moreover, a significant trend is found among the teachers to deny that these verbal behavior techniques are only useful for students up to the primary grade. This shows that these techniques can be equally useful for the middle and higher classes. The analysis has

also shown that there is a low trend of hiring certified English language teachers in Pakistan to specifically teach English as a second language to the students in schools. The majority (83%) of the sampled English teachers were non-certified to teach the English language.

The result of more non-certified teachers teaching the English language in the classroom directly relates to the trend of using difficult verbal behavior techniques prior to simple ones. This indicates that if more English Language Teaching certified individuals are hired by the schools, the trend of using complex verbal behavior techniques before simple techniques could be reversed. And this logical use of simpler techniques before the complex ones can improve the understanding and learning of the students. Yazdanmehr & Akbari (2014) shed light on the expertise of the English language teachers in the Iranian context. They found that the outcome of the non-certified, non-professional, or non-expert English language teachers remains lower than that of those who are qualified for Teaching English as a Second Language or any other English Language Teaching certification.

5. Conclusion

The study has analyzed the teaching of English as a second language in the Pakistani context. The phenomenon has been touched from the angle of teaching English through verbal behavior practices of mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbal practices. The study conducted on the English language teachers of the different strata English medium schools based in Lahore, Pakistan showed homogenous results of the use of these techniques. Moreover, English language teachers use the intraverbal technique mostly prior to simple techniques of mands, tacts, and echoics; they face challenges in imparting language to the learners. This clearly shows the lack of training of the English language teachers.

The major issue this study has found is that 83% of English language teachers hired by the schools are without English Language Teaching certification. The study recommends that all public and private schools should hire English Language teachers with English Language Teaching certifications like TEFL, CELTA, and DELTA, etc. The school administration should provide language learning facilities like language laboratories and equipment. Moreover, public and private sectors should devise a syllabus of the English language through verbal behavior techniques and other practices in fashion all over the world. Policymakers, stakeholders, and researchers are urged to carry out research in this field to promote modern-day English language teaching trends augmented by theoretical and practical skills.

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Appendix A

Survey Questionnaire

A Quantitative Study of Teaching ESL through Verbal Behavior Practices in Private Sector High Schools of Lahore, Pakistan

I am a PhD English (Linguistics) scholar at the Department of Linguistics and Communications, School of Liberal Arts, University of Management and Technology, Lahore, Pakistan, and surveying my Research entitled: *A Quantitative Study of Teaching ESL through Verbal Behavior Practices in Private Sector High Schools of Lahore, Pakistan*. I will be grateful if you would like to answer the following few questions as respondents of this study. In accordance with the ethical considerations of research, the participants' identities will not be disclosed at any stage of the study.

Date:

Section 1: Personal Information

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Age: 20-25 26-30 31-35 36-40 41-45 46-50 Above 50
3. Mother tongue (First language):
4. Class:
5. Total years of teaching English:
6. Academic Qualification:
7. Degree/Certificate for English Language Teaching:

Section 2: Teaching English through Verbal Behavior Practices

How often do these statements apply to you for teaching English as a Second Language to your students through verbal behavior practices? Put a tick in the appropriate box.

Practices	Always	Mostly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
I use the Mand-Model (showing model and then giving verbal instructions) technique in the English language classroom.						
I use the tacts (pointing to objects, giving instructions, and then asking for the students' response) technique in the classroom.						

Practices	Always	Mostly	Frequently	Occasionally	Rarely	Never
I apply the echoics (voicing the verbal response in the form of a question) technique in the class.						
Echoics are useful to reinforce the mands and tacts techniques to gauge the performance of students.						
I use the intraverbal (conversation, asking verbal questions) technique in class.						
Students face difficulty with the intraverbal technique.						
I teach these techniques in the order of mands, tacts, echoics, and intraverbal.						
I teach intraverbal technique first, followed by tacts, mands, and echoics.						
These techniques are useful only for primary-level students.						

Adapted from: Mahmood, K. (2020). Academic Writing Challenges of EFL Learners and Teachers' Proficiency in Pakistani Higher Education. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 8(2), 56-76.